

O EFEITO DE CEPAS DE *Agrobacterium tumefaciens* EM CALOS INDUZIDAS PELOS BROTOS DE GENGIBRE (*Zingiber officinale* var. Roscoe) NA PRODUÇÃO DE ALGUNS COMPOSTOS ATIVOS MEDICINAIS ESTIMADOS POR RP-HPLC

THE EFFECT OF *Agrobacterium tumefaciens* STRAINS ON CALLUS INDUCED FROM THE SHOOT TIPS OF GINGER (*Zingiber Officinale* var. Roscoe) IN THE PRODUCTION OF SOME MEDICINAL ACTIVE COMPOUNDS ESTIMATED BY RP-HPLC

تأثير سلالات من بكتريا *Agrobacterium tumefaciens* على الكالس المستحث من البراعم الطرفية لنبات الزنجبيل *Zingiber officinale* var. Roscoe في إنتاج بعض المركبات الفعالة الطبية وتقديرها بتقنية HPLC

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RESUMO

O gengibre (*Zingiber officinale* var. Roscoe) é uma planta medicinal bem conhecida por suas propriedades farmacológicas. Esta pesquisa teve como objetivo estudar o efeito de diferentes concentrações da bactéria *Agrobacterium tumefaciens* sobre calos induzidos das pontas dos brotos do gengibre na produção de alguns compostos medicinais ativos. Calos foram induzidos a partir do cultivo de meias gemas em MS com 2,4-D na concentração de 1 mg/L com BA na concentração de 0,5 mg/L + 500 mg/L PVP. Foi o melhor meio para indução do calo. Um total de 100 mg de calo em desenvolvimento foi coletado e, após cultivo no mesmo meio, com duas semanas de idade, o calo foi tratado com duas cepas de *Agrobacterium* LBA4404 e C58 e três concentrações de 10¹, 10³ e 10⁵ bactérias/mL a cada tentativa. A análise do RP-HPLC mostrou que, quando tratado com a cepa LBA4404, que estava na concentração de 10⁵ bactérias/mL, o maior aumento na quantidade de Zingerone atingiu 0,278 mg/g, seguido de uma concentração de 10¹ bactérias/mL e que deu a maior concentração de Zingerone, 6-gingerol e 6-Shogaol que foram 0,199, 0,099 e 0,069 mg/g, respectivamente. Quanto à cepa C58, o tratamento registrou 10¹ bactérias/mL, a maior concentração de Zingerone 0,240 mg/g, seguida por uma concentração de 10³ bactérias/mL, que foi significativamente superior em fornecer a maior concentração de 6-gingerol e 6-Shogaol, que atingiu 0,053 e 0,027 mg/g, respectivamente. A partir dos resultados do experimento, pode-se considerar que os compostos médicos ativos produzidos pelo tecido caloso induzido *in vitro* podem aumentar quando expostos a estímulos biológicos, uma vez que os compostos medicinalmente ativos podem ser separados, purificados e usados na forma pura, pois são uma fonte natural para a preparação de medicamentos.

Palavras-chave: *zingiber officinale*, Calos, *Agrobacterium tumefaciens*, compostos ativos secundários medicinais, RP-HPLC

ABSTRACT

Ginger (*Zingiber officinale* var. Roscoe) is a medicinal plant well known for its pharmacological properties. This research aimed to study the effect of different concentrations of *Agrobacterium tumefaciens* bacteria on callus induced from the shoot tips of ginger in the production of some active medicinal compounds. Callus was induced from the cultivation of half-buds in MS with 2,4-D at a concentration of 1 mg/L with BA at a concentration of 0.5 mg/L + 500 mg/L PVP. It was the best medium for induced callus. A total of 100 mg of developing callus was taken, and, after cultivation on the same medium, at two weeks of age, the callus was treated with two strains of *Agrobacterium* LBA4404 and C58 and three concentrations of 10¹, 10³ and 10⁵ bacteria/mL each trial. The analysis of RP-HPLC showed that when treated with LBA4404 strain, which was at the concentration of 10⁵

bacteria/mL, the highest increase in the amount of Zingerone reached 0.278 mg/g, followed by a concentration of 10^1 bacteria/mL and which gave the highest concentration of Zingerone, 6-gingerol, and 6-Shogaol which were 0.199, 0.099 and 0.069 mg/g respectively. As for the C58 strain, the treatment recorded 10^1 bacteria /mL, the highest concentration of Zingerone 0.240 mg/g, followed by a concentration of 10^3 bacteria /mL, which was significantly superior in giving the highest concentration of 6-gingerol and 6-Shogaol, which reached 0.053 and 0.027 mg/g respectively. From the results of the experiment, it can be considered that the active medical compounds produced by the induced callus tissue *in vitro* can increase when exposed to biological stimuli, as the medicinally active compounds can be separated, purified and used in a pure form as they are a natural source for drug preparation.

Keywords: *Zingiber officinale*, callus, *agrobacterium tumefaciens*, medicinal secondary active compounds, RP-HPLC

الملخص

الزنجبيل (*Zingiber officinale* var. Roscoe) هو نبات طبي معروف جيداً بخصائصه الدوائية. هدفت الدراسة الحالية إلى تأثير تراكيز مختلفة من بكتريا الأجرعية المورمة *Agrobacterium tumefaciens* على الكالس المستحث من البراعم الطرفية لنبات الزنجبيل في إنتاج بعض المركبات الطبية الفعالة. تم تحفيز الكالس من زراعة انصاف براعم في وسط MS مع وجود 2,4-D بتركيز 1 ملغم / لتر مع BA بتركيز 0.5 ملغم / لتر + 500 ملغم / لتر PVP حيث كان الوسط الافضل لاستحث الكالس. تم أخذ 100 ملغم من الكالس النامي، وتمت زراعته على نفس الوسط، وفي عمر أسبوعين، تمت معاملة الكالس بسائلين من بكتريا *Agrobacterium* وهما LBA4404 و C58 وبثلاثة تراكيز 10^1 و 10^3 و 10^5 خلية بكتيرية/ مل، كل تجربة كانت على حدة. اظهر تحليل HPLC للنتائج عند المعاملة بسلالة LBA4404 بتركيز 10^5 بكتيريا/مل بلغت اعلى زيادة في كمية Zingerone 0.278 ملغم/غم يليها تركيز 10^1 بكتيريا/مل والذي اعطى اعلى تركيز من Zingerone و 6-gingerol و 6-Shogaol والذي كان 0.199 و 0.099 و 0.069 ملغم/غم على التوالي. أما بالنسبة لسلالة C58، فقد سجلت المعاملة 10^1 بكتيريا / مل أعلى تركيز من Zingerone 0.240 ملغم / غم، يليه تركيز 10^3 بكتيريا / مل والذي كان أعلى بكثير في إعطاء أعلى تركيز من 6-gingerol و 6-Shogaol التي بلغت 0.053 و 0.027 ملغم / غم على التوالي. من نتائج التجربة يتضح أن المركبات الثانوية الطبية التي ينتجها نسيج الكالس المستحث في المختبر يمكن أن تزداد عند تعرضها للمحفزات البيولوجية، حيث يمكن فصل هذه المركبات الطبية الفعالة وتثبيتها واستعمالها بشكل نقي إذ تعتبر مصدر طبيعى لتصنيع الدواء.

الكلمات المفتاحية: الزنجبيل، الكالس، بكتريا الأجرعية المورمة، المركبات الثانوية الطبية الفعالة، تقنية HPLC

1. INTRODUCTION:

Medicinal plants consider from ingredients that can be used in the development and synthesis of drugs. Also, these plants play a critical role in the growth of human cultures around the world, and after the World Health Organization announced the need to return to natural herbal treatment and reduce the intake of chemically manufactured treatments as their negative side effects (Mekuriya and Mekibib, 2018; Rasool Hassan, 2012). Among these plants is the ginger plant, which belongs to the family of Zingiberaceae, one of the largest monocotyledon families, which includes many medicinal plants, including *Curcuma longa* L. and *Elettaria cardamomum* (L.) Maton (Hartati *et al.*, 2014).

Zingiber officinale (ginger) is called the home pharmacy. Ginger produces rhizomes used for medicinal and food purposes (Dhanik *et al.*, 2017). It is one known plant for its frequent use as an alternative medicine since ancient times (Akoachere, 2002). It has been included among medicinal plants for its wide range of therapeutic uses (Sacchetti *et al.*, 2005; FAO, 2013). The chemical analyzes indicate that the *Z. Officinale* plant rhizomes contain 12.3% carbohydrates, 2-3% protein, 2.4% crude fiber, 2-3%, 0.9% fatty oil, and moisture 80.9%. It also contains many

vitamins, such as Riboflavin, Thiamine, Niacin, vitamin B6, vitamin E, and Ascorbic acid. Besides, it contains many essential minerals such as Copper, Zinc, Iron, Calcium, Nickel, Magnesium, Manganese, sodium and potassium, and many chemical active compounds that have therapeutic reasons against many diseases. These active compounds include volatile oils, alkaloids, phenols, flavonoids, glycosides, terpenes, tannins, saponins, and steroids, as main plant materials (Ghasemzadeh *et al.*, 2010; Pilerood and Prakash, 2011; Shahi and Hussain, 2012; Olubunml *et al.*, 2013; Bijaya, 2018). It is used in Greek medicine to treat colds, stomach disorders, rheumatism, nerve diseases, gingivitis, dental pain, asthma, traumas, constipation, diabetes, vomiting, nausea, and seasickness (Wang and Wang, 2005; Tapsell *et al.*, 2006) as well as a tonic for blood circulation (Shoji *et al.*, 1982).

Many bioactive compounds in fresh ginger, including phenolic and terpene compounds, have been identified, such as gingerols, shogaols, paradols and zingerone (Figure 1), responsible for different ginger bioactivities (Gupta *et al.*, 2016). Ginger has been used in traditional medicines for the treatment of gastric issues. Ginger's distinctive pungency is caused by the so-called active components Shogaols, Zingerone, and Gingerols (Stoner, 2013). Gingerols can be transformed into

corresponding Shogaols with heat treatment or long term storage. Shogaols can be transformed into Paradols after hydrogenation (Gopi *et al.*, 2016). Gingerols mainly contribute to the pungency of the raw material of the ginger. In the ginger raw material, there is mainly 6-,8-,10-gingerol, 6-, 8- Shogaol (Semwal *et al.*, 2015). The most common chemical constituent found in ginger is 6-gingerol, which provides much of the desired flavor and aroma and many medicinal properties found in ginger. Also known as 5-hydroxy-1-(4-hydroxy-3-methoxyphenyl) decan-3-one, 6-gingerol has a $C_{17}H_{26}O_4$ chemical formula and a molecular weight of 294.3859 (Rahmani *et al.*, 2014). 6-Shogaol, the dehydrated form of gingerol, has many precious pharmacological properties as well. Shogaol is known as (E)-1-(4-Hydroxy-3-methoxyphenyl) dec-4-en-3-one and has a $C_{17}H_{24}O_3$ molecular formula and a molecular weight of 276.388 (Jung *et al.*, 2018). Zingerone is present in ginger in a significant quantity of about 9.25%. It is a member of the family of Methoxyphenols and their related derivatives. They have a basic phenolic ring attached to the benzene ring with a methoxy group. It is known that Zingerone has potent pharmacological activities (Zhang *et al.*, 2012). Zingerone is mainly present in dry ginger, but the retro-aldol reaction also converts gingerol (another component in ginger) into zingerone by cooking or drying. The use of high-profile liquid chromatography has shown that the 6-gingerol, 8-gingerol, and 10-gingerol content is generally low in fresh ginger while the amount of zingerone increases significantly when drying and roasting (Ahmad *et al.*, 2015).

Studies have developed in introducing tissue culture technology to increase the production of secondary active compounds from some medicinal plants compared to the quantities extracted from the whole plant (Oomah, 2003). Biotechnology is used in the agricultural, industrial and medical fields and in the production of useful compounds under controlled conditions and the extraction of effective substances with medicinal uses from the calculus of plants throughout the year without being bound by the growing season (Park *et al.*, 2008). These active compounds can be increased in callus induced from plant parts separated and cultivated *in vitro* when subjected to biotic and abiotic stimulation. These active compounds can be separated, purified, and used in a pure manner (Collin, 2001; Bisset, 2007).

This study aimed to increase the secondary active compounds in the ginger plant through treatment with *Agrobacterium*

tumefaciens.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS:

This study was carried out in the laboratory of plant tissue culture in the College of Agriculture and the laboratories of the College of Pharmacy University of Basrah, Iraq.

2.1. Callus induced

Callus was induced from planting half-buds of the ginger plant (Figure 2) in MS (Murashige and Skoog) medium provided with 2,4-D (2,4-Dichlorophenoxy acetic acid) at a concentration of 1 mg/L with BA (Benzyl Adenine) and 0.5 mg/L + 500 mg/L with PVP (Polyvinyl Pyrrolidone) as it was the best medium for callus induction (Al-Taha *et al.*, 2020). A total of 100 mg of developing callus was taken and implanted on the same medium after two weeks of inoculation of the wounded callus with bacterial suspensions of *A. tumefaciens* of the strains LBA 4404 and C58 (Figure 3).

2.2. Preparing bacterial isolates

A. tumefaciens of the strains LBA4404 and C58 were activated on solid medium (Luria Bertani-LB), and after sterilizing the medium with an autoclave, the antibiotic Rifampicin was added at a concentration of 0.025 μ L. The plates were then incubated in a refrigerated incubator at 28°C for 48 hours (Figure 4) (Morgan *et al.*, 1987). The bacterial suspensions were made using the Nutrient Broth (NB) medium. The bacterial suspensions were selected at a concentration of 0, 10¹, 10³, 10⁵ bacteria /mL with the knowledge of the bacterial density shown in table 1.

2.3. Secondary active compounds estimation by HPLC

A total of 20 mg of the standard active compounds of ginger Zingerone, 6-gingerol, and 6-Shogaol were obtained from the Chinese company Shyuanyi yuanye Bio-tognologe with 98% purity. For the RP-HPLC Analysis, it was diluted with 500 μ L of pure ethanol 99.5% per active compound and mixed well using a Vortex mixer to get 0.13, 0.14, and 0.20 Molar respectively, then was kept in the refrigerator at 4°C to the next step. Plant extracts were prepared following the standard method (Ketel, 1986). Fresh weight (10 g) was taken from the resulting callus, washed well with distilled water, dried with filter paper, and cut well. The samples were

crushed well, placed in Petri dishes, and stored at -4°C for 48 hours. Then they were lyophilized by freeze dryer for 24 hours. 1 g of dried sample was dissolved in 5 mL ethanol and kept in the dark for 12 hours at 20±3°C. The next step was shaking the samples well using the Vortex mixing to ensure its dissolution. The dissolved samples were centrifuged, filtered then placed in the refrigerator in the dark until the secondary active compounds 6-gingerol, 6-Shogaol and Zingerone were measured in plant extracts by HPLC. A total of 30 µL of the three standard solutions 6-gingerol, 6-shogaol and Zingerone (10 µL per active compound) were withdrawn and injected together into HPLC.

2.4. HPLC analysis

HPLC type 100 LC-UV 100 Plus Angstrom determines the retention time and sample pack height of the standard solutions (Zhang *et al.*, 2013). The following conditions were set:

- Stationary phase: Nucesil 100-S
- Column: Arcus type (4.6 × 250 mm)
- Temperature for Column: 30°C
- Mobile Phase: Acetonitrile and Water HPLC in a 50:50 V: V ratio.
- Flow rate: 1 mL / min.
- Wavelength: 282 nm.

The concentrations of secondary active compounds were quantified using a comparison between the standard active compound and the sample under the same laboratory conditions using equation 1 (Almukhtar, 2017).

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

Figure 5 shows the retention time and the peak area of the standard Zingerone and 6-gingerol and 6-Shogaol active compounds. The retention time of the three active compounds was 4.61, 9.26, and 11.42 min, respectively, while the peaks area of the active compounds above was 1238074.1, 1891032.8 and 2006960.1, respectively.

3.1. Effect of *A. tumefaciens* strain LBA4404

The results of Table 2 and Figure 6- A, B, C, D and E show that the concentrations of *Agrobacterium tumefaciens* from the LBA4404 strain has a significant effect on the callus content of the secondary three compounds active compounds Zingerone, 6-gingerol and 6-Shogaol.

The treatment of 10⁵ bacteria /mL was significantly superior, resulting in the highest concentration of Zingerone, (0.278) mg/g, followed by a concentration of 10¹ bacteria /mL, which showed the highest concentration of the three active compounds, (0.199, 0.099, 0.069) mg/g dry weight respectively.

3.2. Effect of *A. tumefaciens* strain C58

The results of Table 3 and Figures 7- A-C show that the concentrations of *Agrobacterium tumefaciens* from the C58 strain has a significant effect on the callus content of the three secondary compounds active Zingerone, 6-gingerol, and 6-Shogaol. The treatment of 10¹ bacteria/mL was significantly superior, resulting in the highest concentration of Zingerone, (0.240) mg/g, followed by a concentration of 10³ bacteria/mL, which showed the highest concentration of 6-gingerol and 6-Shogaol (0.053 and 0.027) mg/g dry weight, respectively.

The reason for the superiority of *Agrobacterium tumefaciens* increase the secondary of metabolism in callus tissue that was treated with bacterial suspensions of LBA4404 and C58 may be attributed to the dominance of stable genes in differentiated tissues over the region coding for enzymes needed for biosynthesis and providing the necessary vectors (Akramian *et al.*, 2008). Genetic transformation in wounded callus begins when the bacteria stick to the wounds due to the area to edit tissue cells callus materials phenolic (Acetosyringone) is necessary to stimulate a group of genes *Vir* genes in stable Ti plasmid (Bensaddek *et al.*, 2008). The transfer of a piece of T-DNA from the Ti plasmid and its association with the cell genome randomly results in the addition or deletion of the sequence of base pairs in the DNA of the transformed cells. In this way, the transferred T-DNA segment and depending on the site of its association may cause activation or suppression of some genes in the pathway of secondary metabolite (Alvarez, 2011).

Among the most important genes in T-DNA are Oncogenes carrying the gene group *roIA*, *roIB*, and *roIC* known to be responsible for the growth and differentiation of cells that work either alone or in combination in stimulating the construction of secondary metabolites in the transgenic cells (Bulgakov, 2008). The reason for using *Agrobacterium* rely on the fact it is considered a natural vector because it has a unique ability to confer one or both right RT-DNA or left LT-DNA or both from Ti plasmids and include them in the plant cell genome, causing a change in the metabolism

of auxin and cytokinin in the transgenic callus tissue (Zambryski *et al.*, 1989). Their genetic stability characterizes these transformed plants as they have high growth and are thus an effective means for forming and producing secondary medicinal metabolites (Hu and Du, 2006). That finding is consistent with his findings Rao *et al.* (2012), Singh *et al.* (2014), Tusevski *et al.* (2015), Sajjalaguddam and Paladugu (2016) and Nhut *et al.* (2017) in their studies on *Alpinia galangal*, *Hypericum perforatum*, *Hypericum perforatum*, *Abrus precatorius* L., and *Tagetes spp.* Sequentially, when exposing callus to *A. tumefaciens* and *A. rhizogenes*, they found there was an increase in stimulation of the callus tissue to produce secondary active compounds. This is the first study to observe *A. tumefaciens* on ginger callus in stimulating medicinal secondary active compounds.

4. CONCLUSIONS:

The ginger callus treatment with biotic elicitors (*Agrobacterium tumefaciens*) led to a significant increase in the number of medicinal compounds Zingerone, 6-gingerol and 6-Shogaol compared to the control treatment (untreated callus and fresh ginger). It can be seen that the LBA4404 strain (10^5 bacteria/mL) gives the highest concentration of the Zingerone content, followed by a concentration of 10^1 bacteria/mL that gave the highest concentration of the three active compounds Zingerone, 6-gingerol, and 6-Shogaol. Further, the treatment of 10^1 bacteria/mL of the strain C58 was significantly superior in giving Zingerone the highest concentration, followed by a 10^3 bacteria/mL concentration, which gave the highest concentration 6-gingerol and 6-Shogaol compared with fresh ginger and 0 treatments complement with the control.

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$$\text{Sample con. (mg. gm}^{-1}\text{)} = \frac{\text{sample area}}{\text{standard area}} \times \text{standard solution con.} \times \text{dilution factor} \quad (\text{Eq. 1})$$

Table 1. Bacterial densities of *Agrobacterium* strains used in the study

Inoculate (bacteria /mL)	LBA4404	C58
10 ¹	2 × 10 ³	1 × 10 ³
10 ³	15 × 10 ⁵	25 × 10 ⁴
10 ⁵	2 × 10 ⁷	1 × 10 ⁷

Table 2. Effect of different concentrations of *A. tumefaciens* LBA4404 on ginger plant callus content from secondary active compounds.

Inoculate (bacteria /mL)	Zingerone (mg/g)	6-gingerol (mg/g)	6-Shogaol (mg/g)
fresh ginger	0.014	0.006	0.013
0	0.018	0.009	0.017
10 ¹	0.199	0.099	0.069
10 ³	0.177	0.091	0.064
10 ⁵	0.278	0.066	0.036
L.S.D _{0.01}	0.0025	0.0025	0.0025

Table 3. Effect of different concentrations of *A. tumefaciens* C58 on ginger plant callus content from secondary active compounds.

Inoculate (bacteria /mL)	Zingerone (mg/g)	6-gingerol (mg/g)	6-Shogaol (mg/g)
fresh ginger	0.014	0.006	0.013
0	0.018	0.009	0.017
10 ¹	0.240	0.002	0.003
10 ³	0.015	0.053	0.027
10 ⁵	0.055	0.039	0.002
L.S.D _{0.01}	0.0025	0.0025	0.0025

Figure 1. Major ginger active ingredients and their analogs

Figure 2. Callus induced from planting half-buds of the ginger plant in MS medium provided with 2,4-D at a concentration of 1 mg/L with BA at a concentration of 0.5 mg/L + 500 mg/L PVP

Figure 3. Effect of different levels of *A. tumefaciens*, LBA4404, and C58 in the ginger callus

Figure 4. Bacterial isolates used in the study

Figure 5. Curve chart, retention time, and peak area of standard solutions (Zingerone, 6-gingerol, and 6-Shogaol).

Figure 6-A. Curve chart, retention time, and peak area of fresh ginger and content of secondary active compounds.

Figure 6-B. Curve chart, retention time, and peak area at a concentration of 0 and its effect on the production of secondary active compounds in callus.

Figure 6-C. Curve chart, retention time, and peak area of *A. tumefaciens* LBA4404 strain at a concentration of 10¹ and its effect on producing secondary active compounds in callus.

Figure 6-D: Curve chart, retention time, and peak area of *A. tumefaciens* LBA4404 strain at a concentration of 10³ and its effect on the production of secondary active compounds in callus.

Figure 6-E: Curve chart, retention time, and peak area of *A. tumefaciens* LBA4404 strain at a concentration of 10⁵ and its effect on the production of secondary active compounds in callus

Figure 7-A: Curve chart, retention time, and peak area of *A. tumefaciens* C58 strain at a concentration of 10¹ and its effect on the production of secondary active compounds in callus

Figure 7-B: Curve chart, retention time, and peak area of *A. tumefaciens* C58 strain at a concentration of 10^3 and its effect on the production of secondary active compounds in callus

Figure 7-C: Curve chart, retention time, and peak area of *A. tumefaciens* C58 strain at a concentration of 10^5 and its effect on the production of secondary active compounds in callus.